

Heritage Healing Practices of Mishng, Deori and Ahom Communities of Jorhat District, Assam

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The core of the renowned Ayurveda is found in India's extensive historic practice of using folk medicine. There are around 4000 plant species in the state of Assam, of which 167 are native to the region and 952 are employed in some capacity in medicine. Since ancient times, Assamese indigenous communities have relied on traditional remedies to manage a variety of illnesses. The state's tribes use a variety of plants, both recognised and unrecognised, to cure a range of illnesses. The current research endeavours to find out the traditional remedies that the Mishng, Deori and Ahom population in the Jorhat area of Assam exploit. A questionnaire was created for the study, and some secondary data were also gathered. The survey was conducted between September to December of 2023, and the information gathered was documented along with its ethno-medical applications.

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